

ANALYSIS OF RESIN MATRIX CHANGES DURING COMPOSITE CURE

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The curing of a composite is a dynamic process caused by the constantly changing molecular structure of the resin matrix. This paper discusses the combination of dielectric analysis and differential scanning calorimetry as a means of process development and control on a series of epoxy resins and curing agents of defined chemical structure.

Introduction

Fiber reinforced composites have become an accepted material of construction by a wide variety of industries. The current annual consumption is in excess of 1.4 billion pounds.¹⁾ The manifold advantages of these materials has stimulated broad interest in the aerospace industry. Composites have progressed from use in decorative trim materials to consideration and use in primary structures. The latter has necessitated closer control over the properties of the final part. For a given fiber combination the properties of a properly fabricated composite are dependent on the matrix resin. Knowledge of a proper cure and control of the process has thus become a necessity.

In current practice both control and development of the fabrication process are arrived at empirically. The results reported herein are an investigation of dielectric analysis and differential scanning calorimetry as a means of more precise cure control and development. Together they form a powerful analytical tool to study the thermodynamics of the cure and how the rheology changes as the cure progresses.

Description of the Methods

Dielectric analysis is a method that allows the tracking of the dielectric changes occurring in the resin matrix during cure. These in turn can be related to rheological changes. Because the properties are constantly changing we prefer to use the term dynamic dielectric analysis (DDA).

The change in viscosity of a resin system during cure is important. It governs resin flow and ultimately the fiber to resin ratio as well as the degree of compaction of the composite. Viscosity changes are the result of heating which lowers the viscosity and polymerization which increases the viscosity. These changes can be related to changes in the dipole moment of the resin as it cures. They can be measured in an alternating current field where the resin is the dielectric in a capacitor. Two values are normally observed, capacitance and dissipation factor or loss tangent. The latter will be used as the primary measurement in the following discussion. The method lends itself to monitoring cure during fabrication and studies on cure cycles. There are numerous references in the technical literature which elucidate further on the principles involved⁽²⁻⁷⁾. To better understand this procedure and the results which follow, consider Figure 1. The lower curve describes the dissipation factor changes occurring as the resin cures. The left hand portion records the loss tangent as a function of temperature. The right hand portion relates to events at the cure temperature as a function of time. The resin system in this case is the diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA, I) cured with diaminodiphenylsulfone (DDS, II). The units of the vertical axis have been omitted. The dissipation factor is a dimensionless number. Hence, only the peak locations and not their magnitude are of significance.

Two peaks are observed, A and B. Peak A is concerned with softening of the resin, flow and dissolution of the curing agents. Peak B is associated with the chemistry of the cure, gelation of the resin and eventually total cure, point C. Total cure is defined as the point where the dissipation factor no longer changes with time at constant temperature. Between peaks A and B is a low loss region where pressure is normally applied to the part for compaction and resin content control.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measures the heat of reaction between resin and curing agent. This is possible because as the components react heat is evolved. Using the same horizontal axis the upper curve in Figure 1 defines the heat of reaction. The energy is measured in millicalories/second on the vertical axis. Again the units have been omitted. The current discussion is not concerned with heat of reaction. For cure development studies the important features are reaction rates, completeness

of cure, etc. The polymerization of epoxy resins has been studied by DSC⁸⁾ indicating the feasibility of the method.

At point A' a slight endotherm is noted. This is the result of a small amount of residual solvent in the resin formulation. Heat is required to boil off the solvent. At point B' the exotherm peaks in this case just as the resin arrives at the cure temperature. The area beneath the exotherm curve corresponds to the total amount of reaction between the resin and curing agent. At point C' the DSC curve has returned to the baseline indicating completion of the cure. The DDA and DSC data are in agreement on this point.

Point D' is termed the onset of cure. This is important. Many times during the cure of the composite a hold temperature is required to bring the part to uniform temperature or for debulking purposes. Below D' very little cure occurs. Above D' the cure proceeds at an ever increasing rate.

Resin Systems

For the purposes of this study it was decided to examine the effect of curing agent structure on the cure of an epoxy resin, the diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA, I)^{a)}. To further expand the scope of the investigation four different resins were examined using a common curing agent. The chemical structure of the resins is shown in Figure 2 and the curing agents in Figure 3.

Experimental Results

The results of the DDA and DSC measurements are shown in Figure 1 and Figures 4-13. The salient features of these data, as discussed in the section describing the methods, are presented in Tables I & II. The heat up rate in all cases was 2°C/minute to the indicated cure temperature. Further experimental detail is given in the appendix.

There are several generalizations which are of importance for the discussion which follows. In the figures, it is important to note the relative positions of the second peak of the DDA measurements and the DSC exotherm peak. Changes in the resin or the curing agent vary this relationship. As a general rule epoxy resin systems gel when the reaction between the resin and curing agent is 40-60% complete⁹⁾. This conforms to 40-60% of the area under the exotherm curve from DSC.

In some cases the first peak of the DDA curve is missing. This indicates a low viscosity resin system or the presence of a solvent in the prepreg varnish. This latter point is clearly a) Epon 828, Shell Chemical Co.

illustrated in Figure 12. When the solvent is removed (Curve B) the first peak reappears. Note also that the 2nd peak, which is associated with the cure shifts to the left. This shows that the matrix system B-staged further during the solvent removal.

The curves also demonstrate that DDA and DSC agree fairly well on defining the completion of the cure. The data presented in the Tables show some variations, but this is only for the last few percent of cure. With additional experience using these techniques, differences of this type will undoubtedly be better understood. Also tabulated is a column denoting consolidation temperature. This is the temperature range where pressure should be applied to the part in order to achieve the proper consolidation and correct fiber volume. It was derived through consideration of both the DDA and DSC data. Application of pressure too late in the cure cycle results in a composite with poor consolidation and a low fiber volume. Application of pressure too early in the cycle, depending on the fiber and resin involved, can result in a high fiber volume and a reduction in interlaminar shear strength.

Discussion

Effect of the Curing Agent Structure

Four curing agents were chosen for the purposes of this study: diaminodiphenylsulfone (DDS, II), Nadic methyl anhydride (NMA, III), dicyandiamide (DICY, V) and boron trifluoride monoethylamine complex ($\text{BF}_3\cdot\text{MEA}$, VI). To demonstrate how DDA and DSC can be used together for the purpose of cure development and control, the diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (I) was chosen as the resin component. This is the most commonly used epoxy resin and the curing agent chemistry is well understood.

The DDA and DSC show that catalysts, in all cases, accelerate the chemical reactions involved in the cure. As the data in Table 1 shows, however, the time required for complete cure is not always reduced. This is an important point in processing considerations. An accelerator can reduce processing time but a post cure may be required. Valuable autoclave or press time can be saved; however, the accelerated process will require tighter cure control.

The DSC data defines another point of interest called the cure onset temperature. This is the earliest temperature where a discernible reaction takes place between the resin and the curing agent.

Depending on the size of the composite being fabricated, heat up rates can be quite important. A large part may contain both thick and thin cross sections. It is thus possible to conceive

a situation wherein the thick and thin sections vary widely in temperature. Pressure is applied for consolidation. The thin sections being too warm and too close to the gel point would flow poorly. A weak part would result due to a high resin and a high void content. The thick sections being too cool could lose excessive amounts of resin as the temperature rises. These areas would also be weak and the part fails to meet the engineering specifications. Before the onset temperature, however, the chemical reactions of the cure proceed slowly. Holding the part somewhere below this temperature would permit thick and thin sections to reach temperature equilibrium and minimize the aforementioned problem. With the four curing agents studied note that the onset temperature falls close to the consolidation temperature range.

The onset temperature is also of value when a part must be debulked or compacted during the lay up. This is needed many times in complicated shapes to obtain a low void content fabrication. Heating to temperatures below the onset softens the resin permitting consolidation while minimizing the B-staging.

Attention should be paid to the relative positions of the second DDA peak (Table I) and the DSC exotherm peak (Table II). These can vary considerably. This means that definition of the resin gel point from the dissipation factor curve varies. As defined by DSC, the matrix gels when the degree of resin curing agent reaction is in the neighborhood of 50 percent complete. Thus both DSC and DDA data must be considered for proper assignment of the consolidation temperature range.

In order to further understand the utilization of the DDA, DSC combination each curing agent is considered individually.

Diaminodiphenylsulfone (DDS, II). The DSC data indicates that DDS in the uncatalyzed form is a slow curing agent (Figure 1). The DDA data shows that the first peak, associated with flow, wetting, and curing agent dissolution, occurs at a low temperature and the second or cure peak at a relatively high temperature. This means we have a "forgiving" process. Pressure can be applied over a fairly broad temperature range when required for consolidation of the part. This has been demonstrated in another publication¹⁰). Similar reasoning can be applied to the BF_3 complex catalyzed system (Figure 4); however, the consolidation pressure range is reduced.

An additional clue to proper processing can be drawn from the DSC data. The DSC exotherm peak curve falls below the temperature peak on the DDA curve. This means that gelation of the resin occurs early on the upslope of the second DDA curve. Any consolidation pressure used on a part must be applied before this

point. Failure to do so would give a high void, high resin content composite.

The time to completion of cure derived from the DSC and DDA measurements agrees well for the uncatalyzed system. There is a discrepancy when the resin system is catalyzed. The DDA data indicates a longer cure is needed. The DSC data indicates that the curing reaction is complete after 30 minutes. The latter is a more precise technique and undoubtedly correct. Dielectric measurements can change by means other than further curing reactions such as the evaporation of volatile material.

One final observation of interest can be made from the DSC data. In both cases a small endotherm is noted just below 80°C. This tells the fabricator that a small amount of solvent remains in the resin system. Residual solvent in small quantities can have a pronounced effect on elevated temperature properties of the composite. A long post cure may be needed to evaporate the solvent in order to attain maximum temperature capabilities.

Nadic methyl anhydride (III). Figure 5 shows that this curing agent will not react appreciably with the resin in the absence of an accelerator. However, the choice of accelerator can have considerable influence on the processing conditions. With EMI-24 (IV) (Figure 6) as the accelerator this system cures rapidly. The onset of cure is abrupt and occurs at a higher temperature than the metal salt accelerated system (Figure 7). EMI-24 would be preferred if debulking is part of the process. The DSC data shows a sharp peak which indicates a rapid cure. Autoclave time would be saved but consolidation pressure must be applied over a narrow temperature range. This would require good process control.

The BF_3 complex (Figure 7) has a relatively low onset temperature which is a disadvantage in debulking. It has the advantage of having a broad consolidation temperature range. Thus process control is relatively easy. It would be a good choice for large part production where temperature equilibrium over a large surface could be a problem.

Dicyandiamide (V). DICY (Figure 8) is the most widely used among the latent curing agents. Characteristically, it reacts very rapidly on reaching the onset temperature. Because of this the consolidation pressure must be applied quite rapidly and it finds wide spread use in press molding operations. There are numerous materials which can be used to accelerate this type of resin system. The effects of one of these, a urea type, is shown in Figure 9. As can be seen the curing temperature can be lowered from 177°C to 121°C. The onset of the cure occurs quite rapidly as evidenced from the DSC data.

The DDA data for both the catalyzed and uncatalyzed systems demonstrates another important point. After the second peak the dissipation factor does not drop rapidly to a low value as is the case with the other curing agents. This indicates the resin matrix is above the glass transition temperature (T_g). If the part were removed from the press or autoclave at this temperature considerable distortion could result. Accordingly, the operator would be told to let the part cool below T_g under pressure.

BF_3 monoethylamine complex (VI). This curing agent (Figure 10), being a Lewis acid, has a fair degree of latency. Epoxy prepregs based on BF_3 .MEA have shown utility after 2-3 months storage at room temperature. It has the disadvantage of losing its activity in prepregs containing glass fibers. The alkalinity of the glass tends to neutralize a Lewis acid.

With this particular system cure control, from the standpoint of application of consolidation pressure, could prove difficult. Early in the cure the resin viscosity is quite low. Application of the pressure too soon would undoubtedly afford a dry part. Pressure should be applied after a certain amount of B-staging has occurred during the process. In view of the fairly rapid reaction rate this may be difficult to time exactly. The peak of the DSC curve falls on the upslope of the dissipation factor cure peak. Again, DSC data tells us that gelation probably takes place before the maximum dissipation factor is reached.

Effects of the Resin Structure

In addition to DGEBPA (I) three other resins were examined, an epoxy novolac (EN, VII)^a, and octaglycidyl ether of a bisphenol A novolac BPAEN (VIII)^b, and a cycloaliphatic diepoxide (CA, IX)^c. A common curing agent, BF_3 .MEA, was used with each resin. The three glycidyl ether types display a small peak just above the 100°C on the DSC curve. This apparently results from dissociation of the BF_3 salt. Again for purposes of better understanding the DSC/DDA combination the resins are considered individually.

The Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (I). This resin curing agent combination was discussed in the previous section on curing agents.

The Epoxy Novolac, (VII). The DSC exotherm (Figure 11) occurs at approximately the same temperature as that observed for DGEBPA (I). The cure peak on the dissipation factor curve, however,

a) DEN 438, Dow Chemical Company

b) Epi-Rez Su-8, Celanese Resins

c) ERL 4221, Union Carbide Co., Chemicals and Plastics.

occurs much latter during the cure. This makes selection of the consolidation temperature more difficult. It would probably require some experimentation. Based on DDA alone it would not be unrealistic to consider any temperature between approximately 60 to 170°C. The DSC results narrow the range to 110° to 130°C. There is also disagreement between the DSC and DTA data as to when the cure is complete. By analogy to the curing study the DSC data is probably the best indication.

The Glycidyl ether of the bisphenol A Novolac (VIII). Two of the curves in Figure 12 were obtained directly from the laminating varnish. Curve A is the dielectric analysis of the varnish itself and only the cure peak is visible. The first, or flow peak, is not seen because of the low viscosity of the resin solution. If the solvent is removed (Curve B) the two peaks typical of many prepreg systems are apparent. The second or cure peak has now moved to the left indicating additional B-staging during solvent removal. The two peaks are quite close, indicative of a high melt viscosity which can make processing difficult. Note also that the consolidation temperature range has been narrowed to 120° to 130°C.

The DSC data run on the solvent varnish contains no surprises. An endotherm is noted slightly below 80°C where the solvent boils off. The BF_3 dissociation peak again can be seen at a temperature slightly above 100°C. The exotherm peak falls at about the same place as observed for the other two glycidyl ethers.

The Cycloaliphatic epoxide (IX). This material (Figure 13) behaves entirely differently than the other resins. As a generalization cycloaliphatic epoxides react rapidly under acidic conditions. Because the curing agent is a Lewis acid the curing reaction is quite rapid. The DSC exotherm peak is quite low, 100°C. A composite based on this system would be very difficult, if not impossible, to properly cure under these conditions. Undoubtedly, the material passes from a very fluid state to a gel extremely rapidly.

The DDA data is difficult to correlate with the DSC observations. The two peaks are obviously not those associated with flow and cure as was the case with the glycidyl ethers. It could be explained on the basis of a very high exotherm occurring just after the gelation of the resin resulting in a momentary increase in molecular mobility of the resin mass before the final cure begins. The dissipation data, however, agrees well with the DSC findings on the time to cure completion.

These data suggest strongly that an entirely new cure cycle be considered, possibly a hold on some temperature in the neighborhood of 60-80°C.

Conclusions

Dynamic dielectric analysis and differential scanning calorimetry are useful techniques for assessing the physical nature of a resin matrix at various stages during its cure. Together they form an excellent method for deriving new cure cycles. Dynamic dielectric analysis can be related to the rheological changes which occur in the matrix as it cures and is useful for process control. Differential scanning calorimetry compliments this data by defining where the cure begins, how rapidly the resin and curing agent react as a function of the particular curing cycle and the degree of completeness of the cure at a given temperature.

However, care should be exercised in the interpretation of these data. Rheological interpretation of the dielectric loss tangent data varies as the chemical structures of the curing agent and resin are varied. Thus gelation of the resin does not always occur at the same point on the loss tangent curve. Differential scanning calorimetry confirms this conclusion. From differential scanning calorimetry or dielectric data alone consolidation pressure could be applied too early or too late in the process and a poor part may result. While both procedures are useful in cure studies, the combination of the two affords a more complete picture of the curing process.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Miss Deborah K. Whearty of Lockheed Missiles & Space Company for her valuable technical assistance.

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Appendix

Experimental Details

Dynamic Dielectric Analysis. All determinations were made on a Tetrahedron Associates, Inc. Dielectric Analysis System. The basic instrumentation consisted of an Audrey II, Model 202 dielectrometer, a DI/AN 300 test cell, an ATC 200 temperature controller, a Data Track Model 5310 programmer and a Houston RS-350 recorder.

A 0.4 gm sample of the resin system was weighed into a 2" diameter aluminum dish containing a 2" circle of 181 style glass cloth. A 5 mil layer of Kapton (polyimide) film was placed over the sample. This assembly was placed in the test cell at 100 psi. Using the controller and programmer the sample was then heated at a rate of 2°C/minute to 177°C (350°F) or 121°C (250°F) depending on the resin system. Temperature and dissipation factor were recorded as a function of time to generate the data as presented in the Figures 1 and 4-13.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry. The differential scanning calorimeter was a DuPont Instrument 990 series with a 902 calorimeter. The programmer on the calorimeter was set to heat at a rate of 2°C/minute to 177°C (350°F) or 121°C (250°F) and hold at the selected top temperature. The top temperature was selected on the basis of the resin system involved. A sample weighing approximately 20 mg. was placed in the standard 0.250" aluminum cup and covered. The reference standard was a covered 0.250" aluminum cup. The recorder was set as follows:

Temperature Scale	20°C/inch Chromel-Alumel thermocouple
Scale Y'	1.0 millicalories/inch
Scale Y	0.2 millicalories/inch

Using the two recorder pens in the manner outlined above permitted easy detection of both small and large exotherms within the boundaries of the recorder chart paper. When the upper limit of the temperature was reached the recorder was changed to record on a time basis of 10 inches/minute. No change was made on the Y axis recording. Using this procedure resulted in a facile correlation with the DDA results.

RESINS, STRUCTURES

Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A, DGEBPA

I

Epoxy novolac, EN

VII

Epoxy novolac, bisphenol A based, BPAEN

VIII

3,4-Epoxycyclohexylmethyl-3',4'-epoxycyclohexane
carboxylate, CA

IX

Figure 2

CURING AGENTS, STRUCTURES

Diaminodiphenylsulfone, DDS

II

Nadic methyl anhydride, NMA

III

2-Ethyl-4-methylimidazole, EMI-24

IV

Dicyandiamide, Dicy

V

Boron trifluoride monoethylamine complex, BF₃·MEA

VI

Figure 3

Figure 1. Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (I) cured with diaminodiphenylsulfone

Figure 4. Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (I) cured with diaminodiphenylsulfone (II) accelerated by $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{MEA}$ (VI)

Figure 5. Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (I)
cured with nadic methyl anhydride (III)

Figure 6. Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (I)
cured with nadic methyl anhydride (III)
accelerated by 2-ethyl-4-methylimidazole (IV)

Figure 7. Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (I)
 cured with nadic methyl anhydride (III)
 accelerated by a metal salt

Figure 8. Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (I)
 cured with dicyandiamide (V)

Figure 9. Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (I)
 cured with dicyandiamide (V) using
 a urea type accelerator

Figure 10. Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (I)
 cured with $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{MEA}$ (VI)

Figure 11. Epoxy novolac (VII)
cured with $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{MEA}$ (VI)

Figure 12. Bisphenol A based epoxy novolac (VIII)
cured with $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{MEA}$ (VI)

Figure 13. Cycloaliphatic diepoxide (IX)
cured with $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{MEA}$ (VI)

TABLE I SUMMARY OF DDA DATA

Resin	Curing Agent	Accelerator	Fig. No.	DYNAMIC DIELECTRIC ANALYSIS			Consolidation Temperature °C
				1st Peak °C	2nd Peak °C ^a	Time To Total Cure (Min) ^b	
DGEBPA (I)	DDS (II)	-	1	68	8 min. @177	40	120-130
DGEBPA (I)	DDS (II)	BF ₃ complex	4	40	15 min. @177	> 60	115-120
DGEBPA (I)	NMA (III)	-	5	-	-	-	-
DGEBPA (I)	NMA (III)	EMI-24 (IV)	6	< 40	140	7	100-110
DGEBPA (I)	NMA (III)	Metal Salt	7	55	167	15	80-110
DGEBPA (I)	DICY (V)	-	8	70	28 min. @177	> 60	150-160
DGEBPA (I)	DICY (V)	Urea type	9	60	80 min. @121	> 80	120
DGEBPA (I)	BF ₃ .MEA (VI)	-	10	< 40	170	30	110-120
EN (VII)	BF ₃ .MEA (VI)	-	11	< 40	20 min. @177	> 60	110-130
BPAEN (VIII)	BF ₃ .MEA (VI)	-	12A ^c)	< 41	15 min. @177	> 60	120-130
BPAEN (VIII)	BF ₃ .MEA (VI)	-	12B ^c)	120	177	> 60	-
CA (IX)	BF ₃ .MEA (VI)	-	13	132	175	> 30	60-80

a) When peak is at cure temperature time to peak is indicated.

b) After reaching cure temperature.

c) 12A, DDA shown with solvent, 12B, DDA shown without solvent, dried 1/2 hour at 90°C.

TABLE II SUMMARY OF DSC DATA

Resin	Curing Agent	Accelerator	Fig. No.	DIFFERENTIAL SCANNING CALORIMETRY			Consolidation Temperature °C
				Cure Onset °C	Exotherm Peak °C ^a	Time To Total Cure (Min) ^b	
DGEBPA (I)	DDS (II)	-	1	137	177	40	120-130
DGEBPA (I)	DDS (II)	BF ₃ complex	4	114	152	30	115-120
DGEBPA (I)	NMA (III)	-	5	-	-	-	-
DGEBPA (I)	NMA (III)	EMI-24 (IV)	6	112	140	5	100-110
DGEBPA (I)	NMA (III)	Metal Salt	7	64	142	30	80-110
DGEBPA (I)	DICY (V)	-	8	150	3 min. @ 177	> 60	150-160
DGEBPA (I)	DICY (V)	Urea type	9	108	8 min. @ 121	80	120
DGEBPA (I)	BF ₃ .MEA (VI)	-	10	80	148	30	110-120
EN (VII)	BF ₃ .MEA (VI)	-	11	90	150	> 60	110-130
BPAEN (VIII)	BF ₃ .MEA (VI)	-	12	128	160	> 60	120-130
BPAEN (VIII)	BF ₃ .MEA (VI)	-	12	-	-	-	-
CA (IX)	BF ₃ .MEA (VI)	-	13	70	110	> 30	60-80

a) When peak is at cure temperature time to peak is indicated.

b) After reaching cure temperature.